

Microscopic models of citation network

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Abstract

This paper briefly reviews some of the literature on microscopic models of citation network.

The construction of a model of citation distribution may begin with the following statement: citation distribution does not constitute a goal of a bibliometric study but rather a problem that can only be solved by building a citation model. Published in 1976, the paper [Price(1976)] marked a major breakthrough in citation modeling. Unsurprisingly, subsequent research reveals further improvement in the construction of citation models. It appears impossible and unnecessary for the purposes of this paper to elaborate on all achievements in this area. We would like to refer an interested reader to [Radicchi et al.(2012)Radicchi, Fortunato and Vespignani, Golosovsky(2019), Traag(2022)] for a more detailed overview.

The modeling of citation distributions is fraught with difficulties due to their highly complex genesis. The citation of a single paper is affected by a number of factors including trends in the development of the scientific field and the topic, features of the authors and the journals, etc. Hence the variety of meaningful empirical regularities, which have been subject of structure-oriented mechanistic models of citation networks for decades. Such models give us a cognitive picture complete with a citation frame of reference.

To be a little more precise, let us denote with $P(c)$ the relative number of papers receiving c number of citations. Then the set of numbers $\{P(c_i), i = 1, \dots, n\}$ is called the probability distribution of citations or, briefly, the citation distribution.

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In his seminal work [Price(1976)], Price suggested the so-called cumulative advantage process: highly cited papers accumulate citations faster than papers that are less cited. This mechanism (also known as preferential attachment [Barabási and Albert(1999)]) leads to the “rich get richer” effect. We start from a citation network defined at an integer “time” t . It is assumed that the probability $P(i \rightarrow j)$ of a new paper i to cite a previously published paper j is

$$P(i \rightarrow j) = \frac{k_j + r}{\Omega}, \quad (1)$$

where Ω is the normalization factor, k_j is the number of citations of paper j and the positive constant r is called an initial attractiveness ($r = 1$ in [Price(1976)]) to take care of the fact that hitherto uncited papers also have a chance to be cited. Thus, each paper on average cites b earlier published papers that are selected in proportion to the number k of citations they have already received plus r . The probability that a new edge is attached to a node with the in-degree k is therefore $(k + 1)((b + 1)t)^{-1}$. By $P(c, s, t)$ we denote the probability that the s th paper has c citations at the time t . The rate equation satisfied by $P(c, s, t)$ is

$$P(c, s, t + 1) = cP(c - 1, s, t)\frac{b}{(b + 1)t} + \left(1 - \frac{b(c + 1)}{(b + 1)t}\right) P(c, s, t). \quad (2)$$

The probability of the total citation distribution $P(c, t)$ can be written as the sum

$$P(c, t) = \frac{1}{t + 1} \sum_{s=0}^t P(c, s, t). \quad (3)$$

Substituting Eq.(3) in Eq.(2), we get

$$(t + 1)P(c, t + 1) - tP(c, t) = \left(cP(c - 1, t) - (c + 1)P(c, t)\frac{b}{b + 1}\right) + \delta_{c,0}, \quad (4)$$

where the Kronecker delta $\delta_{c,0}$ (which adds a single paper if $c = 0$, but none otherwise) originates from the boundary term $P(n, s = t + 1, t + 1)$. After that one can obtain the stationary solution $P(c, t) = P(c, t + 1) = (cP(c - 1) + (c + 1)P(c)b(b + 1)^{-1} + \delta_{c,0})$, and the expected probability $P(c)$ can be calculated as

$$P(c) = \frac{c(c - 1) \cdots 1}{(c + 2 + b^{-1})(c + 1 + b^{-1}) \cdots (3 + b^{-1})} P(0).$$

Now if we recall $P(0) = (b + 1)(2b + 1)^{-1}$, we get

$$P(c) = (1 + b^{-1}) B(c + 1, 2 + b^{-1}). \quad (5)$$

Here $B(\alpha, \beta) = \Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)/\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)$ is the Euler beta function, and

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty x^\alpha \exp(-x) dx$$

is the standard gamma function. For large values of α , the value of $B(\alpha, \beta)$ is close to $\alpha^{-\beta}$.

Price found that the right tail of citation distribution decays in a power-law manner, i.e. ($c \gg c_{\min}$): $P(c) \propto c^{-\nu}$, with the exponent ν belonging to the interval [2.5, 3.0]. (However, [Laherrère and Sornette(1998)] introduced a different form of citation distribution: a stretched exponential function $P(c) \propto \exp(- (c_0^{-1}c)^\nu)$.) Since $r \neq 1$, it follows that [Krapivsky and Redner(2001), Dorogovtsev and Mendes(2002), Newman(2003)]

$$P(c) = \frac{B(c + r, 2 + rb^{-1})}{B(r, 1 + rb^{-1})}. \quad (6)$$

Clearly, if $c \rightarrow \infty$, then the equation Eq.(6) gives a power law for large c with the exponent $2 + rb^{-1}$.

The preferential attachment approach Eq.(1) suggests a rather simplified citation model. It is directly succeeded by the generalized preferential attachment approach, which allows for non-linear effects [Krapivsky and Redner(2001)] and aging [Hajra and Sen(2006), Wang et al.(2008)Wang, Yu and Yu, Newman(2009), Wu et al.(2014)Wu, Fu and Chiu]. Thus, the probability $P(i \rightarrow j)$ of a new paper i to cite a previously published paper j can be written as

$$P(i \rightarrow j) = \frac{a(\Delta t) (k_j + r)^\gamma}{\Omega} \quad (7)$$

Here $a(\Delta t)$ is the aging function, $\Delta t = t_i - t_j$ is the age of the paper j with respect to the paper i , and γ is the attachment exponent.

Further development of the preferential attachment model revealed its need for modification (see, e.g., [Newman(2009), Newman(2014), Ke et al.(2015)Ke, Ferrara, Radicchi and Flammini, Piva et al.(2021)Piva, Ribeiro and Mata]). An important step in this direction was made through the introduction of fitness [Bianconi and Barabási(2001)], an

empirical attribute that measures the ability of a paper to receive citations. Normally, fitness is an empirical attribute, discoverable empirically, although attempts have been made to tie it, for example, to the PageRank coefficient [Zhou et al.(2016)Zhou, Zeng, Fan and Di]. In the most general form within the framework of the fitness-based preferential attachment model, the equation for $P(i \rightarrow j)$ can be written as follows (see [Wang et al.(2013)Wang, Song and Barabási], and [Pham et al.(2015)Pham, Sheridan and Shimodaira], and [Pham et al.(2016)Pham, Sheridan and Shimodaira])

$$P(i \rightarrow j) = \frac{\phi_j a_j(t) (k_j + r)^\gamma}{\Omega}, \quad (8)$$

where ϕ_j is the fitness of the paper j , r is the initial interactivity, $a_j(t)$ is the aging function, and γ is the attachment exponent.

Importantly, the fitness can also be introduced in the additive manner [Eom and Fortunato(2011)]: $P(i \rightarrow j) = (k_j + \phi_j) \Omega^{-1}$.

Subsequent development of microscopic models of citation produced the copying mechanism [Vazquez(2001), Krapivsky and Redner(2005), Simkin and Roychowdhury(2012)]. The mechanism can be represented as follows [Peterson et al.(2010)Peterson, Pressé and Dill]. While writing a new paper, the actor who cites is likely to build on the work of a predecessor. For example, the paper may concern dark matter. The actor who cites may well access an already published paper on the subject and copy one of its references (which may seem random to a bystander). However, instead of copying somebody else's reference, the actor who cites may cite a selected predecessor quite at random (as a bystander may believe). The copying mechanism leads to the following formula for the probability $P(i \rightarrow j)$ of a new paper i to cite a previously published paper j

$$P(i \rightarrow j) = \frac{\alpha + \beta k_j}{\Omega}, \quad (9)$$

where α is the probability of random search, and βk_j is the probability of copying. In the simplest case, $\alpha \Omega^{-1} = n^{-1}$ and $\beta k_j \Omega^{-1} = \beta c (bn)^{-1}$, where b is the reference number of each new paper, c is the number of citations that the old paper j has received, and n denotes the number of existing papers in the network. The equation Eq.(9) therefore

conveniently reduces to $P(c) = (1 - \beta)bn^{-1} + \beta cn^{-1}$, the solution of which is

$$P(c) \approx \frac{(\theta + \beta^{-1})^{(\theta+1)\beta^{-1}}}{(\theta\beta + 1)(\theta - 1)^{\theta-1}} \left(\frac{\theta - 1 + c}{(\theta + 1)(\beta + c)^{-1}} \right)^{\theta+c} \frac{(\theta + \beta^{-1} + c)^{\beta^{-1}}}{(\theta - 1 + c)}, \quad (10)$$

where $\theta = b\beta^{-1} - b$. The citation distribution $P(c)$ in the asymptotic approximation ($c \gg \theta$) of Eq.(10) can be obtained straightforwardly as expressed below

$$P(c) \approx \left(\frac{(\theta + \beta^{-1})^{\theta+\beta^{-1}} \exp(-1 + \beta^{-1})}{(\theta\beta + 1)(\theta - 1)^{\theta-1}} \right) c^{-(1+\beta^{-1})}. \quad (11)$$

If $c \simeq \theta$, the citation distribution $P(c)$ becomes a power-law with the exponent $\nu = 1 + \beta^{-1}$.

Later, a more complex stochastic model of citations was proposed which is based on the copying, redirection and triadic closure mechanism [Golosovsky(2019), Golosovsky(2021)]. Golosovsky concluded that the distribution of citations is compatible with a lognormal distribution (LN for short) given by $f(c) = (\sqrt{2\pi}c\sigma)^{-1} \exp(-(\ln c - \mu)^2\sigma^{-2})$ (here $f(\cdot)$ is the probability density function).

Despite considerable research efforts, microscopic mechanistic models of citation networks are only loosely connected with empirical data [Okamura(2021), Traag(2022)]. The most highlighted study theme is the asymptotic approximation of the right tails of citation distributions. Microscopic mechanistic citation models may be referred to as “semiquantitative”.

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